

Differentiation of Two Trehalase Activities Present in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* by Copper

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Manuscript received 20 January 1995, revised 26 May 1995, accepted 13 July 1995

Presence of two different trehalases in response to their interaction with Cu^{2+} has been demonstrated in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Trehalase, extracted from vegetative cells, is found to be inhibited by the presence of Cu^{2+} (2 mM) while the other extracted from germinating cells is activated by the same. Increase in trehalase activity together with increase in intracellular c-AMP and glucose level has been noticed at the onset of spore germination. Optimum trehalase activity (germinating) is noticed at pH 5.0, temperature 35° and in presence of 2 mM Cu^{2+} . The enzyme has relatively low K_m (0.385 mM). The results suggest that it is an acid trehalase (non-regulatory trehalase). Enzyme solution containing Cu^{2+} (2 mM) is found to be more stable against exposures to various temperatures and pHs in comparison to enzyme solution without Cu^{2+} . So the role of Cu^{2+} appears to be providing stability to the trehalase molecule.

Trehalose (α -D-glucopyranosyl- α -D-glucopyranoside) is an important disaccharide widely distributed in bacteria, yeasts, fungi and insects¹. Accumulation of trehalose in fungi is associated in general with periods of reduced growth rate, i.e. in derepressed stationary phase cells or during sporulation, or nutrient starvation, or temperature stress etc.²⁻⁴. The only enzyme known to be responsible for trehalose hydrolysis is trehalase (α , α -trehalose-1-D-glucosylhydrolase E.C. 3.2.1.28)². Since trehalose metabolism and morphological differentiation occur simultaneously in yeast, the regulation of trehalase activity is an extremely important event inside the cell. Moreover, trehalose metabolism is possibly analogous to glycogen metabolism. Studies on this enzyme revealed that two different trehalases can be discerned: a nonregulatory enzyme and a regulatory enzyme². The nonregulatory trehalase has an acid pH optima, lower K_m (0.5–3.0 mM), relatively higher heat stability and requires no cofactor. On the other hand, the regulatory trehalase with neutral pH optima is relatively less heat-stable, has higher K_m (around 4.8 mM or more) and was reported to be activated through c-AMP dependent protein phosphorylation^{2,5}. However, more data are needed before any firm conclusion can be drawn regarding the existence of a correlation between the K_m and the type of trehalase.

Both regulatory and nonregulatory trehalases are shown to be present in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*⁶⁻⁸. Differentiation of trehalase enzyme in response to the effect of EDTA and NaCl on the enzyme activity has been reported⁹. Unfortunately, the regulatory mechanism for the acid trehalase (nonregulatory enzyme) is still not clearly understood. In this context we become interested in characterising a nonregulatory trehalase so that work on the regulation of nonregulatory enzyme may be undertaken in future.

Results and Discussion

Approximately 1.5-fold decrease in the enzyme acti-

ity was observed after dialysis. Only Cu^{2+} and Mg^{2+} appeared to be beneficial for the enzyme among which the former being more effective (Table 1). About 1.5-fold increase in enzyme activity was noticed by the presence of

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT CATIONS ON TREHALASE ACTIVITY*

Addition (2.5 mM)	Activity ($U \cdot 10^{-3}/\text{mg} \pm \text{SEM}$)			
	Germinating ^a		Normal ^b	
	Undialysed	Dialysed	Undialysed	Dialysed
Nil	29.3 \pm 0.5	19.1 \pm 0.4	14.1 \pm 0.2	9.4 \pm 0.5
$\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	42.5 \pm 1.0	26.4 \pm 0.6	14.8 \pm 0.5	9.9 \pm 0.3
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	61.2 \pm 1.8	78.2 \pm 2.0	1.0 \pm 0.2	0.7 \pm 0.1
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ + $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	71.0 \pm 1.8	9.4 \pm 1.8	1.2 \pm 0.3	0.8 \pm 0.2

*Cations (2.5 mM) tested as $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, NaCl, $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ remained without of any effect on trehalase activity (15 min preincubation). Trehalase activity was measured as described in the text with modifications as Cu^{2+} and Mg^{2+} was omitted from the assay mixture but added separately to test their effects individually. Values represented were average of two sets of duplicates \pm standard error of mean (SEM).

^aEnzyme solution was prepared from spores germinated for 1 h. ^bEnzyme solution was prepared from vegetative cells (mid-logarithmic phase).

Mg^{2+} only while 2.1-fold (undialysed) and 4.1-fold (dialysed) increase in enzyme activity could be obtained by Cu^{2+} alone. This increase in activity could be further enhanced by the coexistence of both the cations. In contrast, the enzyme extracted from vegetative cells was found to be inhibited significantly by the same Cu^{2+} (Table 1). So, in reference to the effect of Cu^{2+} , two different trehalases are present in this yeast though their differential interaction with Cu^{2+} is not yet known.

As mentioned earlier, reports regarding differential interaction of trehalase enzymes with EDTA or NaCl is available⁹. But we could not find any such effect on enzymes prepared from either germinating cells or vegetative cells. In this connection it is to be mentioned that report regard-

Fig. 1. Change in trehalase activity with change in glucose and c-AMP level during spore germination. Germinating spores were taken out at intervals and enzyme solution was prepared as stated earlier. Trehalase activity present intracellularly (—O—) was determined. Intracellular c-AMP (—□—) and glucose level (—Δ—) present in both germinating cells and vegetative cells were extracted by perchloric acid²⁰. Briefly, around 1.0 g cells (wet wt.) were washed with water and extracted with 0.5 N perchloric acid at 0–4, brought to pH around 4.5 using 2 N KOH and centrifuged. Supernatants were lyophilised and dissolved in water for analysis. c-AMP content was determined using a c-AMP assay kit according to the technical bulletin provided by the manufacturer (Amersham, England). Glucose was estimated by glucose oxidase-peroxidase method¹⁹. Values represented were mean ± standard error of mean (SEM) of two sets of duplicates (bars). Zero concentration of c-AMP or glucose were values not detectable under the assay condition.

ing the activation of an extracellular conidial trehalase by Ca²⁺, Co²⁺ and Mn²⁺ is available while Cu²⁺ is reported to be ineffective¹⁰. But trehalase from *Dictyostelium* sp. was reported to be inhibited (13%) by CuSO₄ (1 mM)¹¹. Since both Cu²⁺ and Mg²⁺ appeared to be beneficial for the activity, all our subsequent assay mixtures contained both cations.

Change in trehalase activity during germination : In comparison to vegetative cells spores contained about 4.5 times higher trehalase activity. Around 1.4 times increase in activity was observed after 1 h when the spores were subjected to germination (Fig. 1). Thereafter it came down to 0.64 times by 7.5 h. Glucose or nitrogen induced activation of trehalase (≈10-fold increase) was reported for an acetate grown yeast strain *S. cerevisiae* Y55^{3,12}. Glucose and c-AMP induced activation of neutral trehalase has been demonstrated in derepressed cells of *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*⁴. Both group of workers reported that the activation of trehalase was due to post-translational protein modification and so both were neutral trehalases. We noticed that intracellular c-AMP and glucose concentration increased by the same 1 h time period of spore germination when acid trehalase activity increased only 1.4 times. Direct relationship between increase in trehalase activity and increase in intracellular c-AMP concentration at the

onset of growth has been demonstrated for a strain of *S. cerevisiae*¹³. Subsequent experiments revealed that c-AMP and ATP had no effect on this trehalase isolated from germinating cells and Cu²⁺ appeared to be beneficial (Table 2). Our result regarding this little change in trehalase activity is in contrast to other reports and so this was possible an acid trehalase (nonregulatory enzyme). In this connection it may be mentioned that trehalose accumulated during heat stress must be degraded by neutral trehalase during return to normal growth temperature¹⁴. So increase in acid treha-

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF C-AMP AND ATP ON TREHALASE ACTIVITY*

Addition (2.5 mM)	Trehalase activity (U × 10 ⁻³ /mg) ± SEM	
	Germinating** (Dialysed)	Vegetative** (Dialysed)
Nil	21.5 ± 1.1	7.9 ± 0.2
Mg ²⁺ , ATP, c-AMP	36.2 ± 0.8	8.4 ± 0.1
Mg ²⁺ , ATP ^a , c-AMP ^a , Cu ²⁺	83.7 ± 1.5	0

*Enzyme assay etc. were the same as Table 1.

**Same as Table 1.

^aFinal concentration of ATP and c-AMP used in to the assay mixture was 0.10 and 0.01 mM respectively.

lase activity is not expected at the onset of spore germination. Hence introduction of Cu²⁺ in to the assay mixture allowed us to measure only acid trehalase activity.

Physicochemical properties and optimum activity : Optimum activity was obtained in presence of Cu²⁺ (2 mM) but it decreased with further increase in Cu²⁺ concentration (Fig. 2). About three-fold lower activity was obtained when assayed in absence of Cu²⁺. Maximum activity could be measured at pH 5.0 and temperature 35°, resembling acid trehalases (nonregulatory enzyme) as reported by other^{6,15}. No activity could be detected below pH 3.0, temperature 5°

Fig. 2. Trehalase activity as a function of Cu²⁺ concentration. Activity was measured after pre-incubation (15 min) in presence of different amount of Cu²⁺ (0–10 mM). The values are mean ± SEM of three sets of duplicates (bars).

and above pH 8.0, temperature 75° (plot not shown). Around 60% decrease in activity in comparison to the optimum value, was noticed when measured at pH 4.0 or 7.0. Similarly, about 50% less activity was noticed when measured at temperature 20° or at 55°. Michaelis constant (K_m) for the hydrolysis of α, α -trehalose at pH 6.2 as determined from Lineweaver-Burk plot (not shown), was found to be 0.385 mM. This is again analogous to a baker's yeast trehalase (acid trehalase)⁶ but about ten-fold lower than that of an interconvertible trehalase (neutral trehalase)⁵.

Among the substrates tested D-lactose, D-maltose, methyl- α, α -D-glucopyranoside remained unattacked by the enzyme while sucrose was hydrolysed similar to α, α -trehalose. This should not be considered seriously since the enzyme solution was a crude preparation. Reports regarding the inhibition of trehalase activity by acetate, inorganic phosphate, and D-mannitol are available^{2,9,10}. Among these, only D-mannitol (0.5 mM) could cause 16% inhibition of activity but D-glucosamine (0.5 mM) had no effect. The effect of Cu^{2+} might be mediated through its interaction with cysteine residue present (if any) in the enzyme protein. So, when tested separately, *N*-ethylmaleimide or 4-(hydroxymercury)benzoate (sodium) could produce 26 and 24% inhibition of activity respectively.

Effect of copper towards stability of the enzyme : Trehalase solution containing Cu^{2+} appeared to be stable against heat (50°) while in absence of Cu^{2+} about 32% of original activity was lost (Fig. 3). However, stability was found to be falling rapidly when exposed to temperature above 50°. Rate of inactivation of this trehalase was almost 25% higher in absence of Cu^{2+} (Fig. 3, inset). On the other

Fig. 3. Thermal stability of trehalase. Thermal stability of the enzyme (in presence of Mg^{2+} , 2.5 mM) was studied both in presence (—○—) or in absence (—□—) of 2.0 mM Cu^{2+} by preincubating the enzyme solution for 15 min at pH 6.2 and at various temperatures (30–70). Control was an enzyme solution never exposed to any treatment. Thermal stability as a function of time was similarly studied by preincubating enzyme solution at 60° both in presence or in absence of Cu^{2+} (in-set). Aliquots were withdrawn at intervals (0–60 min). Residual activity of these pre-incubated enzyme solutions were determined by measuring the free reducing groups liberated. Values presented are mean \pm SEM of two sets of duplicates.

hand, it appeared to be very much stable when kept at around pH 4.5 and temperature 30° in presence of Cu^{2+} (Fig. 4). About 75% of original activity was lost when exposed to pH lower than 3 or higher than 7. The enzyme appeared to be quite stable in presence of Cu^{2+} when exposed to a pH of 6.2 for 3 h (Fig. 4, inset). About 46% of original activity was found to be lost by the same 3 h time period when Cu^{2+} was absent. On the whole, Cu^{2+} appeared to be providing stability to the enzyme against pH- or heat-inactivation. Hence, Cu^{2+} is a very useful cation for this acid trehalase (nonregulatory enzyme) and probably this is the first report regarding differentiation of trehalases using Cu^{2+} in the assay protocol.

Fig. 4. Stability of trehalase at various pH values. Stability (in presence of Mg^{2+}) of the enzyme at various pHs (2–10) was determined by pre-incubating the enzyme solution for 15 min at 30° in presence of 2 mM Cu^{2+} only. Stability of the enzyme solution at pH 6.2 as a function of time was studied at 30° both in presence (—○—) or in absence (—□—) of Cu^{2+} (in-set). Residual trehalase activity of these pre-incubated samples were determined by measuring the free reducing groups liberated.

Experimental

The diploid strain used was derived from *S. cerevisiae* strains 8534-10A (MAT α , leu 2, ura 3, his 4) and 6460-8D (MAT α met 3)¹⁶. Stock cultures were maintained in YPDA (yeast extract 0.5%, bacto-peptone 1.0%, glucose 2.0%, agar 2.0%, pH 5.5) and grown at $29 \pm 1^\circ$. Starter cultures were grown in YPD medium (no agar) on a rotary shaker (350 rpm and throw of 3.5 cm). Pre-sporulating and sporulating media were derived from available reports¹⁷. Spores were germinated by suspending the water-washed spores in YPD medium using the same rotary shaker.

Both germinating and vegetative cells were harvested separately, washed with water and suspended in potassium phosphate (10 mmol), buffer containing EDTA (1.0 mM), 2-mercaptoethanol (15 mM), phenyl methyl sulphonyl fluoride (2.0 mM), bezamidine hydrochloride (2.0 mM), pH 7.5 (buffer A). Cells were disrupted by passing through a French pressure cell (SLM Instruments, U.S.A.) at 18,000 psi and checked under a microscope. After the cells were broken, pH of the solution dropped down to 4.5–5.0. The

homogenate was then centrifuged at 10000g for 5 min and the residue was discarded since it contained only 5% of total activity. The supernatant containing about 90% of total activity was then dialysed extensively against buffer A and was used mostly (unless specifically mentioned) as enzyme solution. Enzyme solution used during most of the experiments was prepared from yeast spores subjected to germination for 1 h.

The protein content was determined by Coomassie Blue protein assay reagent using bovine serum albumin as standard according to manufacturer's technical bulletin (Pierce, U.S.A.).

Enzyme assay mixture (0.08 ml) consisted of enzyme protein taken in 100 mM Pipes buffer of pH 6.2 containing $MgSO_4$ (2.5 mM), $CuSO_4$ (2.0 mM) and trehalose (13.2 mM) and was incubated at 30° for 30 min. The reaction was terminated by placing the assay tubes in a boiling water-bath for 5 min. Glucose liberated enzymically was determined in terms of free reducing groups¹⁸. Intracellular glucose concentration was measured by glucose oxidase-peroxidase method¹⁹. Unit of enzyme activity (*U*) is defined as the amount that liberates 1 μ m of glucose per min under the assay condition. Specific activity was expressed as units per mg of enzyme protein.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. A. N. Bhaduri, Director of the Institute and Dr. S. Sengupta, Head of the Department for valuable suggestions while carrying out this investigation. Financial assistance to one of the authors (N.B.) from U.G.C., New Delhi and from this Institute (C.S.I.R.) is gratefully acknowledged.

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